

SOME COMMENTS ON THE HISTORY OF WOMEN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7877987>

Abstract: This article reflects some comments on women's history. Also, information on women's history was analyzed on the basis of scientific literature and archival materials within the region.

Key words: Women, gender factor, research, population, society.

In the 70s of the 20th century, "women's history" appeared as a new direction in world historiography and gained its own relevance. The formation of "Women's history" as a main direction was caused by the interests of researchers who studied the history of mass movements. During the study of the "History of Women and Girls", relevant specialists realized the need to take into account the gender factor in social research. Gender history is a manifestation of an interdisciplinary approach in historical research, aimed at restoring the integrity of the new social history. The subject of gender history is the relationship between men and women, which is one of the important aspects of social relations, and their manifestation in the macro-historical context. The dynamics of gender relations are included in the general concept of socio-historical development.

In the former union, until 1985, not only gender studies, but also "women's history" did not exist as an independent field. At the same time, the first studies were carried out in the USSR. But this issue was not supported by the scientific community. In the former Soviet Union, "women's history" has been studied to some extent by sociologists, jurists, demographers, and ethnographers in applied social sciences.

At the end of the 80s of the 20th century, feminist literature in English began to be translated in the former union. In 1990, the Center for Gender Studies was established in Moscow as a scientific branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Such centers began to operate in 1991 in St. Petersburg (under the university and at the branch of the Institute of Sociological Research of the Russian Academy of Sciences), and in 1992 in other cities. These centers first of all united sociologists, economists and lawyers, partly ethnologists, medical workers, psychologists. Especially, during the last twenty-five years, great attention has been paid to the study of "women's history" - issues of gender equality. Even magazines have special columns on the subject, and many studies are published each year on different periods and regions. For example, the researches of the famous scientist N.L. Pushkareva and philosophers J. Lacan, J. Derrida and Y. Kristeva and L. Irigarey were related to gender history[1].

In Uzbekistan, from the mid-90s of the 20th century, representatives of the field of social science began to deal with the history of gender. In 2003, the basic concepts and terms of gender theory and feminism were reflected in the "Gender Research Fundamentals Course Chrestomatum"[2]. At the same time, excerpts from works popular in the West on the theoretical and methodological foundations of gender studies have been translated into

Uzbek. The collection "Introduction to the theory and practice of gender relations", published in 2007, contains articles on the theory and methodology of gender studies in various scientific areas, including economics, education, law, history, politics and culture [3]. Among them, the scientific research of Marianna Camp, an American researcher dedicated to the emancipation of women in Uzbekistan, is particularly important.

Later, journalist and researcher M. Tokhtakhojaeva shed light on the historical events of the 20th century based on oral stories, letters and diaries of women of different professions and ages in Uzbekistan[4].

In the last decade, the issue of gender equality has been given special importance in Uzbek historiography[5] and foreign studies[6].

Elizabeth Constantine's doctoral dissertation on "Public discourse and private life: Uzbek women and Soviet rule, 1917-1991" at Indiana University, USA, in 1917-1991. changes in these issues were reflected[7].

The article by D. Kandioti and N. Azimova, specialists in gender studies, discusses the participation of Uzbek women in religious ceremonies, the changes in this regard during the Soviet era and the years of independence. In the article, the data obtained as a result of field research among the population in Andijan, Kashkadarya and Khorezm regions in 1997-2001 are included for scientific consumption [8]. Also, in her research, N. Khidirova paid attention to the study of judicial documents on the family-marital relations of the Central Asian khanates of the 16th - early 20th centuries from a historical point of view and, based on the information contained in them, to determine the place of women who lived in the Middle Ages in the social, economic, legal, and cultural life of the society [9].

When researching the history of gender equality issues, many examples can be given from different stages and areas of the history of Uzbekistan. For example, we can take the issue of gender equality in the field of medicine in Turkestan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. In particular, our people have had their own traditional medical knowledge (folk medicine) since ancient times. At the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, European medical institutions entered the life of the people of Turkestan. This situation brought about unique changes in the lives of local women. In particular, at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, providing medical care to women in Turkestan was considered one of the biggest problems.

The first special medical institution for women in Turkestan was opened in Tashkent in 1883. Until that time, women only rarely consulted male doctors[10]. Only female medical staff served in the outpatient clinic established in the "old city" part of Tashkent. 2 female doctors and 1 female paramedic worked in this clinic. From the first years, local women began to apply to this medical center.

Such hospitals appeared in Andijan, Margilon, Namangan, Kokon after 1885[11]. By 1900, a second outpatient clinic was opened in the Beshyogoch part of Tashkent to provide medical care to local women and children. Not only women, but also unmarried girls applied to the established hospitals. For example, in 1885, 149 girls were treated in the outpatient clinic opened for women in Tashkent.

In December 1916, the opening of the gynecology department under the surgical department of the Tashkent city hospital was an important event in the provision of medical care to women. Initially, women from the Russian-speaking population of Tashkent applied to this hospital, but later local women also began to come seeking medical help [12].

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, a number of efforts were made to provide medical care to women in Turkestan, and the establishment of modern medical institutions for them can be considered a positive thing. Local women have access to some modern medical services along with traditional ones. However, the established dispensaries and hospitals were few in number and could not meet the demand. And their situation was difficult from the financial point of view. In addition, the lack of knowledge of local languages and the lack of translators made it difficult for women to receive medical care. It should be noted that according to the rules of Islam, women are not forbidden to consult a male doctor. But they could receive medical care from a male doctor for a wound or pain in the private parts, if it was related to the danger of death or if a female doctor could not be found.

In general, a gender approach can be used in the in-depth study of various fields. In particular, gender studies play an important role in the study of political history. Even in the study of the history of everyday life, revealing the gender aspects of the issue helps to draw deep scientific conclusions.

In short, paying special attention to the history of women in the study of different stages of the history of Uzbekistan allows to better understand the daily life and the social life of the relevant period. Also, the study of the processes within the framework of gender equality serves to fill the pages of the history of Uzbekistan and enrich the imagination in this regard.

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